

Seed treatment with calcium peroxide to control green leafhopper (GLH) and brown planthopper (BPH)

R.F. Macatula, R.P. Basilio, and O. Mochida, Entomology Department, IRRI

Direct seeding with pregerminated rice seedlings is becoming popular in the Philippines because of high labor costs for transplanting. Calcium peroxide has been used as a coating material to prevent poor germination of rice seeds broadcast directly in flooded fields. In a test of germination of IR36 seed at IRRI, at a 1:1 ratio of calcium peroxide and seeds, 66% germinated.

We evaluated seven insecticides in the laboratory. IR22 seeds presoaked 24 h were coated with each chemical at 0.5 kg ai/50 kg seeds and afterwards with calcium peroxide at 1:1 by weight. The seeds were sown in 25-cm-diam clay pots with 5 cm standing water. Ten newly emerged GLH and BPH adults were placed inside each mylar film cage at 10 d after sowing (DAS) and then every 5 d to 30 DAS. Mortality was recorded 48 h after infestation.

Isofenphos and carbosulfan showed good results (Table 1).

In a second test, we evaluated isofenphos and carbosulfan at 0.5 kg ai/50 kg seeds with and without calcium peroxide. There was no significant difference in mortality of BPH and GLH.

In a field test, isofenphos and carbosulfan with calcium peroxide were evaluated at 5 rates: 0.4, 0.5, 0.6, 0.8, and 1.0 kg ai/ 50 kg seeds. Seeds were sown in 30-m² plots with 5 cm standing water. At 11 DAS, then every 5 d to 41 DAS, 20 GLH and 20 BPH adults were caged together on each plot.

Significantly higher BPH and GLH mortalities were obtained on seedlings from seeds treated with insecticide + calcium peroxide, even at 0.4 kg ai/50 kg seeds, up to 28 d after treatment than on seedlings with calcium peroxide alone. Carbosulfan was slightly better (Table 2). □

Table 1. Laboratory evaluation of 7 insecticides and calcium peroxide (cal-per) as seed treatment for BPH and GLH control. IRRI, 1983.

Chemical ^a	Mortality (%) at indicated days after treatment ^b		
	12	22	32
	<i>BPH</i>		
Isofenphos + cal-per	90.0 a	90.0 a	82.5 a
Carbosulfan + cal-per	85.0 a	97.5 a	65.0 a
Chlorpyrifos + cal-per	7.5 b	2.5 b	7.5 b
Acephate + cal-per	7.5 b	5.0 b	7.5 b
Fenthion + cal-per	2.5 b	0.0 b	0.0 b
Carbofuran + cal-per	0.0 b	12.5 b	0.0 b
Prothofos + cal-per	0.0 b	10.0 b	5.0 b
Cal-per alone	0.0 b	5.0 b	2.5 b
	<i>GLH</i>		
Isofenphos + cal-per	77.5 a	65.0 b	80.0 a
Carbosulfan + cal-per	75.0 a	85.0 a	57.5 a
Acephate + cal-per	50.0 b	12.5 c	7.5 b
Carbofuran + cal-per	12.5 c	12.5 c	7.5 b
Prothofos + cal-per	0.0 d	12.5 c	0.0 b
Chlorpyrifos + cal-per	0.0 d	10.0 c	7.5 b
Fenthion + cal-per	0.0 d	7.5 c	0.0 b
Cal-per alone	0.0 d	10.0 c	0.5 b

^a Applied at 0.50 kg ai/50 kg seed. Cal-per : seed ratio was 1:1 by weight. ^b In a column within a species, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT. Av of 4 replications, 10 adults/replication.

Table 2. Field evaluation of seeds soaked in 2 insecticides plus calcium peroxide (cal-per) against BPH and GLH. IRRI, 1984.^a

Insecticide	Rate (kg ai/50 kg dry seed)	Adult female mortality ^b (%)			
		13	23	33	43
		<i>BPH</i>			
Carbosulfan + cal-per	0.4	60 a	73 a	28 a	16 ab
Carbosulfan + cal-per	0.6	64 a	75 a	30 a	15 ab
Carbosulfan + cal-per	1.0	60 a	75 a	43 a	23 a
Isofenphos + cal-per	0.4	54 a	65 a	30 a	16 ab
Isofenphos + cal-per	0.6	54 a	60 a	33 a	19 ab
Isofenphos + cal-per	1.0	46 a	68 a	50 a	18 ab
Cal-per alone	–	15 b	15 b	23 a	6 b
		<i>GLH</i>			
Carbosulfan + cal-per	0.4	56 a	63 a	48 ab	21 a
Carbosulfan + cal-per	0.6	46 ab	61 a	58 a	25 a
Carbosulfan + cal-per	1.0	56 a	69 a	43 ab	28 a
Isofenphos + cal-per	0.4	41 ab	58 a	38 b	23 a
Isofenphos + cal-per	0.6	46 ab	54 a	33 b	18 ab
Isofenphos + cal-per	1.0	40 ab	64 a	50 ab	25 a
Cal-per alone	–	24 b	13 b	23 b	9 b

^a IR22 was direct seeded 11 Jan 1984. Av of 4 replications, 20 adults/replication. ^b Recorded 48 h after caging at 13, 23, 33, and 43 d after treatment. In a column within each species, means followed by a common letter are not significantly different at 5% level by DMRT.

Rice whorl maggot (RWM) damage produces unfilled grains

A.T. Barrion and J.A. Litsinger, Entomology Department, IRRI

RWM *Hydrellia philippina* Ferino is an important vegetative stage rice pest

in wetlands. The female fly normally lays eggs singly on leaf surfaces of seedlings in standing water.

We observed RWM oviposit on booting stage rice. Neonate larvae moved down and settled inside the bulging base of the leaf sheath to avoid